

**TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL
MOTIVATION AMONG FUTURE TEACHERS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF
TEACHING THE MODULE “TEACHING CHILDREN STAGE AND
CREATIVE ACTIVITIES”)**

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Abstrakt: This article describes the formation of professional motivation among future educators-teachers. The article deals with the organization of research works for students of the Faculty of Preschool Education, provides recommendations for the development of improved mechanisms and manuals based on a methodological approach to the development of professional motivation of students of higher educational institutions in teaching activities and suggests an organizational structure for the development of professional qualities.

Keywords: educator, formation, motive, professional motivation, activity, process, attitude, justified, future.

The formation of professional motivation among future educators is an urgent pedagogical problem, the foreign experience of the formation of professional motivation is systematized, the description and analysis of the practice of preparing future educators-teachers for professional activity is systematized.

In this regard, in higher pedagogical educational and research institutions, it is of urgent importance to conduct large-scale scientific research on the development of professional motivation among future teachers, awareness of innovative processes and the formation of a professional position in relation to them, decision-making in the field of professional competencies.

The relevance of the study is characterized by providing reasonable reasons for the formation of professional motivation and the unavailability of future educators-teachers for pedagogical activity:

- - ignoring their individual psychological characteristics in the formation of professional motivation of future educators;
- - lack of continuous and consistent transfer of theoretical and practical knowledge in the formation of professional motivation of future educators;
- - lack of creation of a motivational environment in the educational process on the part of the teaching staff when teaching the “TCHTA” module;
- lack of systematization of educational tasks aimed at purposeful formation of professional motivation among future educators-teachers in the process of learning the module “TCHTA”;
- - the lack of optimal conditions in the learning process for future educators, teachers, allowing to turn external motivation into internal;
- effective methods, forms and means, strategies and technologies aimed at the formation of professional motivation of future educators-teachers in the process of learning the “TCHTA” module have not been identified and put into practice;
- the model of formation of professional motivation among future educators-teachers has not been improved.

The elimination of these causes is an urgent issue because future educators should: create conditions for the creative activity of children in preschool educational organizations; identify and form their abilities for art; create conditions for the constant participation of theatrical and other activities in the pedagogical process; spiritually educate children, familiarity with the environment, enrich their emotional world, concentration and interest in creativity; development of communicative relations, formation of skills to listen to others and work with feedback; to gain an understanding and perception of the

rich cultural and spiritual heritage of our people and teach them to appreciate; introducing children to theatrical culture, mastering the ways of practical implementation of such skills and abilities are important for their successful professional activity. When forming professional motivation for future educators, it is advisable to give scientific and methodological knowledge on the concepts of the stage and staging.

Motive is the main reason that motivates a person to certain actions. And the main reason that motivates a person to work is his needs. The need motivates a person to engage in a certain activity. The product of educational activity arises on the basis of various motives. Motivation as a psychological phenomenon is a complex process in all respects, which also plays an important role in determining a person's life path. Motivation is a dynamic process of psychological and physiological behavior management, including initiative, orientation, organization, and support. Motives are divided into internal and external.

The qualitative effectiveness of the formation of professional motivation among future educators-teachers is guaranteed by the following pedagogical conditions:

firstly, the sequence and implementation of pedagogical actions at all stages of the educational process;

secondly, the ability to use the necessary means of training in the module "teaching children to stage and creative activities" (dolls, characters, stage decorations);

thirdly, the wide use of the possibilities of collective joint activity in the educational process;

fourth, the organization of professional behavior of the right conscious, the formation of skills to carry out professional activities;

fifth, focus on professional self-development and self-education;

sixth, to improve the professional skills of a future specialist based on

social experience.

When forming the professional motivation of future educators-teachers in the process of higher education, it is advisable to implement the following requirements: strengthening the theoretical and cognitive knowledge of students; formation of skills for organizing didactic processes based on psychological and pedagogical knowledge in pedagogical activity, as well as skills and abilities to apply various technologies in the education of preschool children.

Summarizing the results of the research work on the dissertation on the topic "Technologies for the formation of professional motivation among future teachers" (on the example of teaching the module "ODSTD") and evaluating the effectiveness of the results, the following conclusions were made:

1. Comprehensive professional, intellectual, moral-aesthetic and spiritual-moral development of students by improving the existing theoretical and didactic support for the formation of professional motivation among future educators based on modern methods, historical data, international experience is an urgent pedagogical problem of educational importance.

2. The results of this dissertation will serve to systematize innovative methods of forming professional motivation among future teachers-educators based on optimizing the content of the practice of higher preschool education, developing a didactic system for the formation of professional motivation and scientific substantiation of its components.

3. When designing the integration of theoretical and practical classes, improving the professional motivation of future teachers-educators based on the method of motivational induction and the priority of personality-oriented learning, the harmonious development of the components of professional motivation (motive, professional need, professional interest, psycho-emotional readiness for professional activity) is important, which strengthens the mechanism of preparing students for professional pedagogical activities.

4. When applying technologies for the formation of professional motivation of future teachers-educators in the process of qualification and pedagogical practice, it is important to include elements of art pedagogy, such as music, fairy tale therapy, in the content of the educational process.

5. The model developed on the basis of the research results for the formation of professional motivation among future educators serves as a basic resource for students and teaching staff in finding the final results expected from practice, choosing ways to achieve them.

6. The results of the analysis show that the pedagogical and psychological conditions for the formation of professional motivation of future educators are associated with professional qualities, such as activity, responsibility, correct goal-setting and self-development based on an individual professional development program for predictive analysis of methodological gaps in students through the "student to student mentor" approach, which, in turn, depends on depending on the educational situation, in connection with which it is advisable to pay attention to the compatibility of various forms, methods and technologies for the formation of professional motivation among future teachers.

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